

HISTORY OF THE APPLICATION AND STUDY OF DIGITAL GEOGRAPHIC DICTATIONS

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Abstract: The use of active methods in education is one of the current problems of education. Therefore, the use of geographical dictations in the educational process activates the functional process of students' learning.

Relevance of the topic: There are various ways in the methodology of geography education to determine the level of acquisition of the quality of geographical knowledge, skills and skills that should be mastered by students in school geography education in recent years. Determining the level of acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities of students in geography is therefore necessary to identify gaps in students' knowledge, skills and abilities and to fill these gaps. The use of active methods in education is one of the current problems of education. Therefore, the use of geographical dictations in the educational process activates the functional process of students' learning. Experience The use of geographic dictations in the educational process is considered an effective method in geography education and ensures the effectiveness of the following educational activities in students.

1. The student encourages young people to think and study independently in the course of the lesson and extracurricular education.
2. The student helps young people to improve their logical thinking skills during the geography lesson.
3. The use of geographic dictations in the educational process helps students to have an idea of the internal structure of a geographic object, events and processes, as well as its external appearance.
4. The use of geographical dictations in the educational process helps students to have an idea about the internal structure of a geographical object, as well as its external appearance, by causing events and processes.
5. Using geographical dictations in the educational process, students can think about scientific facts and determine why and for what reason these events and processes occur.
6. The use of geographical dictations in the educational process leads to the improvement of the scientific-geographic outlook of students.
7. Using geographical dictations in the educational process, the student will be able to independently distinguish the main concept from the text of the main topic in the textbook.
8. The student's interest in mastering the content of geographical concepts and events will increase.
9. The use of geographical dictations in the educational process will further develop students' resourcefulness.

Knowing the level of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students during the lesson is a criterion for evaluating the level of the lesson. The science of didactics and geography teaching methodology has developed many methods for determining the level of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students. However, even if these educational methods are convenient, they require a lot of time and labor, and their effectiveness is considered to be very low. The activity of students in performing digital geographic dictations, the effectiveness of the work often depends on the assigned task. Therefore, there are certain requirements for performing digital geographic dictations:

1. It can be aimed at reflecting the ideas of important concepts, causal connections, worldviews, that is, at fulfilling the educational goals of the course topics.
2. Assignments should cover all components of knowledge (general and specific concepts, cause-and-effect relationships, laws, facts, issues of interaction between nature and society, methods of education and mental activity).
3. Various educational tools: textbooks, additional literature (newspapers, magazines, popular scientific books, chrestomats), photos, pictures, photographs, screen guides, TV broadcasts, samples of minerals, along with histographic cards of various contents. , herbariums, to ensure the formation of independent pushing skills with statistical data.
4. Digital geographical dictation to develop students' cognitive abilities and allow them to think creatively.
5. Arousing students' interest in geography.

Digital geographic dictation of students is effective only if it is carried out regularly and based on a well-designed system of tasks.

The use of digital geographic dictations in school geography education was first justified by Moscow Methodist scientist L.N. Kartel in 1976 with his work experience. The concept of geographic dictation is a type of activity performed by a teacher and a student in cooperation, and for its implementation, it is necessary to equip students with the skills to explain to students the technology of implementing this methodology and to implement digital geographic dictations. Otherwise, digital geographic dictations may not be effective. Usually, the term dictation applies to the subjects of the philological series, and it is understood that the text of a certain subject is read expressively by the teacher, and the students understand the text and write down the words they hear in the appropriate notebook. Depending on the amount of orthographic and grammatical errors made in the process of writing dictation, philologists evaluate students' ability to write dictation and grammatical literacy. According to psychologists, associations, that is, interconnections, are formed between the center of sound hearing in the brain of students and the centers that move the hand. The grade of students depends on the strength of this connection.

However, geographical digital dictations conducted in geography classes are fundamentally different from ordinary written dictations in the field of philology in terms of technology and procedure. Geographic digital dictations require special preparation from students. Students should be able to acquire the relevant skills and competencies to perform geographical dictations. The teacher should teach students the technology of working with digital geographic dictation.

What are these differences?

- a very short time is required for conducting digital geographic dictations. It takes 5-10 minutes.

- digital geographical dictation takes very little time. Based on the key, the teacher can check and evaluate the written geographical dictation written by 30 students within 5 minutes.
- unlike philological dictations, digital geographical dictations require little time to conduct and check, so they can be taken at the end of the lesson after a new topic has been explained.
- digital geographical dictations, according to psychologists, stimulate several activity centers in the students' brains: the center of hearing and moving the hand, thinking independently, choosing and placing appropriate numbers, or logical thinking centers associations, i.e. interconnections, are formed between them.
- activities carried out by teachers and students during digital geographic dictation can be divided into several types. They consist of the following stages:
 1. Determining and writing down the main geographical concepts in the text of the geography textbook.
 2. Identifying and extracting topics where digital geographic dictations can be conducted.
 3. Numbering of isolated geographical concepts with double numbers.
 4. Creating questions aimed at revealing the essence of the main geographical concepts in the geographical dictation.
 5. Digital geographic dictation technology or digital geographic dictation procedure:
 - Digital geographic dictations are created by the teacher first. In order to create an understanding of digital geographical dictations, we will explain on the example of a digital dictation named "Spatial relief".

The use of digital geographic dictations in school geography education dates back to the seventies of the last century. L.N. Kartel from Moscow was able to prove scientifically and methodologically that digital geographical dictations are an effective method of using in geography education. The use of digital geographic dictations in school geography education was first justified by Moscow Methodist scientist L.N. Kartel in 1976 with his work experience. In his opinion, the most effective and short-term control method for ensuring the thorough acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities of students in geography courses is digital geographical dictations. L.N. Kartel developed the methodology of practical application of digital geographic dictations and based the methodology of its application in natural geography courses. Teaching students to use geographic dictation, especially numerical geographic dictation, from the beginning of natural geography courses will have an effective effect on making this method more effective later on.

The method of practical application of digital geographical dictations in the scientific works of I.S. Sergeyev emphasizes that it is effective in the application of local history materials in the elementary course of natural geography. The practical application of digital geographical dictations is a highly effective method for getting orientation in a place, place plan, scale, lithosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere and the great geographer in illuminating the life and work done by tourists in the way of science.

M.I. Samokhin and G.S. Asonova in their scientific methodical articles were able to reveal the importance of determining the level of students' learning of concepts and laws in "Social, social and economic geography courses" in the practical application of digital geographical dictations. They emphasize that digital geographic dictation is a method that helps students consciously apply social and economic phenomena and processes and reveal the essence of phenomena. T. R. Gerasimova and L. P. Safonov have highlighted in their scientific works that they achieved high results using digital geographical dictation of events and processes in the

courses of "Socio-economic geography of the world". It is emphasized that the use of digital geographical dictations in the course "Socio-economic geography of the world" allows students to remember statistical economic data for a long time and is an invaluable method that allows to quickly determine the solution of economic geographical laws. B.S. Dobrozhitskiy and B.A. Kondratev in their scientific methodical articles describe digital geographical dictation as a quick method of controlling students' knowledge, skills and abilities and their geographical knowledge. Scientifically and methodologically, digital geographic dictations have scientifically and methodologically justified the fact that they are of great practical importance in the study of certain topics and strengthening the lesson in the course "Socio-economic geography of the world".

The contribution of Uzbek Methodist-geographers in the issue of using digital geographical dictations in the "Economic and Social Geography of Uzbekistan" courses is very great. rich scientific treatises and works of accomplished Uzbek Methodist scholars Payoz Musayev, Rustam Gurbaniozov, Qayum Bahromov, Muhyiddin Nabikhanov, Roza Gaipova, Askarali Khaitov and others are dedicated to the use of digital geographical dictations in the courses of "Economic and Social Geography of Uzbekistan". Dozens of their followers and students are effectively using digital geographic dictations in the "Economic and Social Geography of Uzbekistan" courses in geography classes at schools.

I creatively used the work experience of scientists and school geography teachers in different regions on the use of digital geographic dictations and created digital geographic dictations on some topics in the "Economic and Social Geography of Uzbekistan" course. The use of active methods in education is one of the current problems of education. Therefore, the use of geographical dictations in the educational process activates the functional process of students' learning. Experience The use of geographic dictations in the educational process is considered an effective method in geography education and has ensured the effectiveness of educational activities for students. It has been confirmed in practice that using digital geographic dictation is an effective method for determining students' knowledge, skills and abilities. Technologies for practical application of digital geographic dictations have been developed. When using the method of digital geographic dictation, the activities of the student and the teacher during the lesson were justified in a scientific methodical way.

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